

THE ACCEPTANCE OF FACIAL CARE & MAKEUP PRODUCTS IN BEAUTY SALONS

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetic is a planning amazingly connected to change or improve the excellence of skin, hair, nails, lips and eyes. Each exposable piece of the human life structures is liable to corrective fascination. So cosmetics have been utilized from antiquated circumstances to present day times; it is utilized by females as well as by guys; It turns out to be an integral part of human-beings from support to grave.

Entering into the beauty salon industry has a lot of potential in order to increase sales and improve brand awareness of the existing product. In order to introduce new products into the salons we see that giving out free samples to the decision maker and having a workshop in order to introduce the product is very important.

After conducting the survey we have understood that the discounts offered to the salons for the products is also very important. Thus it should be ensured that the discounts offered during a particular season is not less than that offered by the competitors.

This report is focusing on one particular city in the country. Here we look into the fact if everyone in the salon is into the business of selling the cosmetic products and is it making sure a good bit of promotion is being carried out.

According to the target population customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them. Majority of the population agrees that a customer's hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them.

The sample size that was taken for this study is 100 respondents the sample size. The analysis we see that Penetration for Makeup Products is easier and thus the market can be approached with the Makeup Product first.

KEYWORDS:

Cosmetic, Acceptance, Brands, Facial care, Co-relation, Regression, Make up products, Competition, Target population.

INTRODUCTION

The new India is young India with the Rapid growth over the last couple of decades India being younger population country the requirements of younger population has attracted International cosmetic manufacturing companies in Indian market. Many of the domestic manufacturing companies are scaling up their quality and production to match the requirements of international needs.

Herbal cosmetics are in great demand in overseas market and many cosmetic products like baby products, herbal cosmetics, and natural therapies have generated huge demand for Indian Products. Modern promotional strategies have also increase the demand for the cosmetics products thanks to

television media, print media and saloons have widely marketed the cosmetics and its significance to the younger population of India.

However, even with the massive surge in the popularity of cosmetic products come statistics shows that the average Indian Consumer spends much lesser on cosmetics than the consumer from various other part of the world. This gives a green pasture of Greater potential market and customers for cosmetics industry in India.

The revenue for the cosmetic industry is majorly with the urban Markets and I tires Cities. This gives a great scope for nurturing the two tier cities, towns, and smaller villages in order to increase their market share

The Cosmetics Industry is a segment within the Beauty and Personal Care industry. According to the GICS classification, it falls under the Household and Personal Goods Industry.

If you look at the worldwide cosmetic industry, sales reach about \$170 Billion dollars a year. It is distributed almost uniformly around the world although the Western world spends a bit more per person than in Asia.

Cosmetics companies manufacture personal care products using natural, herbal and chemical materials purchased from suppliers. These raw materials are experimented on plants and labs to create formulas for substances that improve the quality of personal beauty. These formulas, generally patented, are used in the mass production of cosmetics products.

Most companies related to cosmetics depend on a multi-level distribution strategy, which also includes placing the products with department stores, specialty retailers, pharmacies, salons, spas, freestanding stores, travel retail outlets, websites and mobile applications.

Saloons are one of the major segment for cosmetic and beauty products where the experts opinion and preferences of the customers are highly influenced this research basically focuses on acceptance of beauty salon products and its marketing through saloons.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Kumar (2005) "Exploratory analysis of global cosmetic industry: major players, technology and market trends" in cosmetic industry, design patterns form more prominent interest for comfort and multi-utilitarian items and higher request among those claim to fame customer portions, especially ethnic, young people and children of post war America, are the enter drivers in shading cosmetics. Makers are inclined to seek after "premium-mass" lines that tight the crevice amongst mass and premium items by offering more premium fixings at lessened costs. Likewise, mass-advertisers are actualizing e-business procedures utilizing the Internet as a business channel, for example, Procter and Gamble's Reflect.com, propelled in 2000, and L'Oreal's reestablishment with Star Media Network Inc. to give a Latin American Internet webpage to impersonate customized discussions performed in retail establishments. He concludes by stating that it is judicious to say that significant restorative players need to stress their center brands, select item dispatches and proceed seaward developments, and may likewise require new administration to execute these methodologies.

Aleksandra Lopaciuk (2013) "Global beauty industry trends in 21st century" has stated the interest for cosmetics will continue developing, powered for the most part by the developing markets of Asia and Latin America, what will add to formation of new products, shape new spending designs and maybe even set up new excellence groups. Worldwide cosmetics makers should separate their items to change them to the desires of their new clients, beginning from various, non-Western societies and acting in an unexpected way. Skincare is the section with the greatest development potential. It will remain the leader section on the corrective market throughout the following couple of years. The central component for market achievement will be mass cosmetics deals - they will be setting the tone for the whole market. Developing familiarity with mass cosmetics being practically in the same class as renowned cosmetics will encourage the development of the fragment.

The dispersion structure is changing too, as general stores and hypermarkets and also online deals directly increment their offers in the general market. New item dispatches are situated in an expanding path upon cutting edge research and innovations. Then again, there is a developing interest for natural items, fabricated economically, regularly as indicated by the reasonable exchange rationality.

According to (Barbalova, 2011) in his paper titled "Global beauty and Personal care" has categorized that the global beauty market into five main business segments: skincare, haircare, color (make-up), fragrances and toiletries. These segments are complementary and through their assorted qualities they can fulfill every one of consumers' needs and desires as to cosmetics. Magnificence items can be likewise subdivided into premium and large scale manufacturing segments, as indicated by the brand renowned, cost and dispersion channels utilized. In a worldwide view the mass fragment spoke to 72% of aggregate deals in 2010, while the excellent section represented the staying 28%. The larger part of worldwide premium cosmetics deals is thought inside the created markets (for the most part of US, Japan and France).

J.Vidya Jawahar, Dr.K.Tamizhthyothi (2013) in their study on "consumer attitude towards cosmetic products" depicts how companies are interested to know about customer's attitude towards cosmetics so as to devise strategies to win over competition and buying behaviour of customers. The study confirms that age, occupation, marital status have positive influence towards cosmetic products. They also give us information about how word of mouth influences the consumer's behavior towards cosmetic products.

Kumar, Sameer, Nassie, Cindy Dumoneaux in their study on "comparative innovative business strategies of their major players in cosmetic industry" shows the qualitative study in the global marketplace. Cosmetic companies have targeted the female audience based on the product itself, it also shows how they are accepted by men and hence the study. They also tell us how even men are inclined towards beauty products and would prefer buying them. They also tell us about the strategies adopted by companies towards influencing the customers.

RESEARCH GAP

The above research papers are an overview on how a company influences the customers to buy the beauty product. But none of this above research papers covers the influence on how the beauty salons play a vital role in influencing the sale of the product. We know that India is a country consisting of a young population and it can go on to become a hub of cosmetic industry.

This study mainly focuses on how the beauty products are accepted in beauty salons.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The trends of fashion and styling are constantly changing in today's times, so to be a successful salon owner, you need to be able to keep up to date with what's trending in your industry to be able to advise your clients and meet their expectations, especially younger ones and also the acceptance of the products used in the salons as the customers need to be really convinced about using a particular cosmetic. Hence, there is a need to Study the Acceptance of Facial Care & Makeup Products in Beauty Salons.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is applicable to the owners trying to sell their beauty products in the salons. The scope of the study is limited to the geographical area of Bengaluru. The study will deal with the overall acceptance of facial care products and makeup products in salons.

OBJECTIVES

- Understanding the usage of Cosmetics in Salons within Bengaluru.
- Understanding the sale of Cosmetics in Salons within Bengaluru.
- To understand how entering the beauty salon industry can help the company expand its sales.
- To find the best penetration strategy of cosmetics into Salons in Bengaluru

SAMPLING

Target population: The population that I have targeted is the salon owners. As the topic clearly states that it is the acceptance of beauty products in salons. I have asked the opinion of the salon owners on how they view-beauty products which was judgment sampling in random method was used. In this, I came across about 82 male respondents and 18 female respondents whose salons are located in Bengaluru.

Sample Size- It is not possible to get the opinion of every salon present in Bengaluru due to lack of adequate time and resources. And the sample size that I have taken for my study is about 100 respondents as our sample. The procedure of data collection was done through paper format which was in form of structured questionnaire and this was filled by about 100 owners.

Nature of the Study-The nature of study considered here is the exploratory type. This research type has been chosen because this problem has not been studied clearly. This helps determine the best research design, data collection method and selection of subjects.

Sample Design- Considering the geographical area of Bangalore with 4 zones i.e., east, west, north, south here we are looking into the opinion of salon owners.

Primary Data- Primary data is the original data, which is, collected directly without the help of any previous data. In the present study; primary data has been collected using questionnaires using paper format for analysis, the Structured questionnaire was used which was on the Likert scale (1-5) interpretation, conclusions, and recommendations.

Secondary Data- This is the sources of data, which have been collected, and observed for other purposes. Some information has also been collected from websites and literature survey, booklets, articles, broadcasts etc.

DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis is broadly classified into three, namely Frequency and descriptive statistics.

Test of the adequacy of the sample (KMO) and reliability tools was used.

Decision tools like Chi-square, Co-relation, and regression is used.

KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST

4.29 KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.718
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2213.724
	Df	276
	Sig.	.000

Normally, $0 < KMO < 1$

If $KMO > 0.5$, the sample is adequate.

Here, $KMO = 0.718$ which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with

The Factor Analysis

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Do you prefer selling makeup products at your parlour	1.000	.816
Do you think the customers are satisfied with the makeup products used	1.000	.940
Does your decision to buy make up products affected by the discount offered	1.000	.944
Do you think products used in other salons can be used	1.000	.718
Does bridal makeup constitute the main source of makeup sessions?	1.000	.802
How important is the quality of the product	1.000	.690
How important is brand image of the product	1.000	.612
Which quarter expects maximum sale for makeup sessions?	1.000	.544
Would you prefer offering multiple facial kit services offered in your parlour	1.000	.674
Are you satisfied with the most used facial care products	1.000	.691
Would you prefer selling facial care products in your parlour	1.000	.739
Would you choose international brand over local brand	1.000	.712
Do you prefer using products that are costlier	1.000	.855
Do you ensure the sale of the products in your parlour	1.000	.605
Acceptance of product n service?	1.000	.930
acceptance of make-up products	1.000	.876
Acceptance of facial care	1.000	.943
overall acceptance	1.000	.831

Do you prefer using products of single brand?	1.000	.729
Do you purchase products based on customer demand	1.000	.897
Is the pricing of a salon service affected by the product used	1.000	.522
Do you think your customers hesitate when you use brands that are unknown to them	1.000	.565
Do you promote other company products in your parlour	1.000	.518
Do you ensure sale of products available at your counter	1.000	.553

RELIABILITY STATISTICS

Table Showing Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.829	24

Cronbach alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. Most of the constructs are more than .6 and some are more than 0.7 which shows that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent response to the items of the concerned constructs.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

Table Showing Hypothesis for Product and Services v/s Acceptance

H0: There is no significant relationship between Product and Services and the Acceptance level.

H1: There is significant relationship between Product and Services and the Acceptance level.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	234.669	187	.010
Likelihood Ratio	167.600	187	.843
Linear-by-Linear Association	32.867	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	100		

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (234.669, $p=0.010$) is less than the table value (0.05) we reject the null hypothesis i.e. the alternative hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between Product and Services and the Acceptance level.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between Product and Services and the Acceptance level.

Table Showing Hypothesis for Make up Products v/s Acceptance

H0: There is no significant relationship between make up products and the Acceptance level.

H1: There is significant relationship between make up products and the Acceptance level.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	461.874	187	.000
Likelihood Ratio	225.967	187	.027
Linear-by-Linear Association	66.216	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	100		

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (461.874, $p=0.000$) is less than the table value (0.05) we reject the null hypothesis i.e. the alternative hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between Make up Products and the Acceptance level.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between Make up Products and the Acceptance level.

Table Showing Hypothesis for Facial Care Products v/s Acceptance

H0: There is no significant relationship between facial care products and the Acceptance level.

H1: There is significant relationship between facial care products and the Acceptance level.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	305.325	187	.000
Likelihood Ratio	185.156	187	.524
Linear-by-Linear Association	37.217	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	100		

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (305.325, $p=0.000$) is less than the table value (0.05) we reject the null hypothesis i.e. the alternative hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between facial care Products and the Acceptance level.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between facial care Products and the Acceptance level.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table Showing Correlation Coefficient of Acceptance on the Other Three Dimensions

		Products and services	Make up products	Facial care products
Acceptance	Pearson Correlation	.576**	.818**	.613**
	Sig (2- tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

INFERENCE

As per the above table, the correlations of Acceptance with all the three analysed dimensions (i.e. Products and services, make up products and facial care products) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It also shows that the null hypothesis is rejected for all the dimensions and therefore there is significant relationship between acceptance and the other dimensions. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between acceptance and dimensions such as product and services, makeup products and facial care products is moderate.

Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.866 ^a	.749	.742	1.23129

Predictors: (Constant), sum of facial care, Sum of the product?, Sum of makeup product

The adjusted R square value is 0.866. This means that the regression analysis can explain 86.6 % of the data and how close it is to the regression line. As such, product and

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

There is sum of each dimension to test for this study and regression analysis.

It is assumed that the selection and buying of apparel are dependent on product and services, makeup products, facial care products and the overall acceptance. To test this hypothesis multiple regression analysis was conducted with sum of product and services, makeup products, facial care products (independent variable) and overall acceptance (Dependent variable).

services, makeup products, a facial care product is highly dependent on the acceptance.

TABLE SHOWING ANOVA

	Mode	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	435.297	3	145.099	95.707	.000 ^b
	Residual	145.543	96	1.516		
	Total	580.840	99			
a. Dependent Variable: sum of acceptance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), sum of facial care, Sum of the product?, Sum of makeup product						

In the analysis of variance table (ANOVA) we test the null hypothesis, i.e. there is No impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables against the alternate hypothesis, i.e. product and services, makeup products, facial care products does not have an impact over Acceptance. The p value from the ANOVA table is 0.000 which is less than the significance value of 0.05 and this leads us to reject the null hypothesis, in other words we accept the alternate hypothesis and say that there exists a significant impact of product and services, makeup products, facial care products on the acceptance.

The p value $0.000 < \text{significance value of } 0.05$ and thus we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which in this case is product and services, makeup products, facial care products and acceptance are dependent on each other.

CHART FINDINGS

According to the target population 14 of them disagree that they prefer using single brand products, and 30 of them agree that they prefer using single brand products and 29 neither agree nor disagree that they prefer using single brand products. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that they prefer a single brand product.

According to the target population 11 of them disagree that they purchase products based on customer demand, and 38 of them agree that they purchase products based on customer demand and 23 neither agree nor disagree that they purchase products based on customer demand. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that they purchase products based on customer demand.

According to the target population 8 of them disagree that a salon service affected by the product used, and

34 of them agree that a salon service affected by the product used and 24 neither agree nor disagree that a salon service affected by the product used. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that a salon service affected by the product used.

According to the target population 8 of them disagree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them, and 31 of them agree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them and 24 neither agree nor disagree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that a customer's hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them.

According to the target population 13 of them disagree that they promote other company products in their parlour, and 42 of them agree that they promote other company products in their parlour and 22 neither agree nor disagree that they promote other company products in their parlour. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that they promote other company products in their parlour.

According to the target population 18 of them disagree that they ensure sale of products available at their counter, and 20 of them agree that they ensure sale of products available at their counter and 34 neither agree nor disagree that they ensure sale of products available at their counter. Therefore the majority of the population neither agrees nor disagree that they ensure sale of products available at their counter.

According to the target population 41 restock their product often and 10 don't restock their product often. Therefore the majority of the restock their product often.

According to the target population 24 pay by cash and 20 pay by cheque and 13 pay by DD and 34 pay by other methods

According to the target population 36 of them tell that hair products are sold the most whereas the rest say that beauty care, skin care and facial care products are sold the most.

According to the target population 19 of them disagree that they prefer selling makeup products at their parlour, and 37 of them agree that they prefer selling makeup products at their parlour and 25 neither agree nor disagree that they prefer selling makeup products at their parlour. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that they prefer selling makeup products at their parlour.

According to the target population 10 of them disagree that customers are satisfied with the makeup products used, and 35 of them agree that customers are satisfied with the makeup products used and 23 neither agree nor disagree that customers are satisfied with the makeup products used. Therefore the majority of the population agrees customers are satisfied with the makeup products used.

According to the target population 6 of them disagree that their decision to buy make up products affected by the discount offered, and 45 of them agree that their decision to buy make up products affected by the discount offered and 29 neither agree nor disagree that their decision to buy make up products affected by the discount offered. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that their decision to buy make up products affected by the discount offered.

According to the target population 10 of them disagree that products used in other salons can be used, and 40 of them agree that products used in other salons can be used and 27 neither agree nor disagree that products used in

other salons can be used. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that products used in other salons can be used.

According to the target population 14 of them disagree bridal makeup constitute the main source of makeup sessions, and 28 of them agree that bridal makeup constitute the main source of makeup sessions and 33 neither agree nor disagree that bridal makeup constitute the main source of makeup sessions. Therefore the majority of the population neither agrees nor disagree that bridal makeup constitute the main source of makeup sessions.

According to the target population 56 of them disagree that quality of the product is important, and 36 of them agree that quality of the product is important. Therefore the majority of the population disagrees quality of the product is important.

According to the target population 2 of them agree that brand image of the product is important, and 46 neither agree nor disagree that brand image of the product is important. Therefore the majority of the population neither agree nor disagree that brand image of the product is important.

According to the target population 84 of them say yes that they satisfied with the number of makeup sessions happening every month, and 10 of them say no they satisfied with the number of makeup sessions happening every month. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that a they satisfied with the number of makeup sessions happening every month.

According to the target population 48 agree that their maximum sales is in the months of January-April, 34 of them agree that their sales is high in the month of May-August and the rest 14 agree that their sales are high in the month of September-December.

According to the target population 10 of them disagree that they prefer offering multiple facial kit services offered in your parlour, and 42 of them agree that they prefer offering multiple facial kit services offered in your parlour and 20 neither agree nor disagree that they prefer offering multiple facial kit services offered in your parlour. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that a they prefer offering multiple facial kit services offered in your parlour.

According to the target population 3 of them disagree that they are satisfied with the most used facial care products, and 44 of them agree that that they are satisfied with the most used facial care products and 14 neither agree nor disagree that that they are satisfied with the most used facial care products. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that that they are satisfied with the most used facial care products.

According to the target population 8 of them disagree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them, and 31 of them agree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them and 24 neither agree nor disagree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that a customer's hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them.

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According to the target population 14 of them disagree that they ensure the sale of the products in their parlour, and 22 of them agree that they ensure the sale of the products in their parlour and 42 neither agree nor disagree that they ensure the sale of the products in their parlour. Therefore the majority of the population neither agrees nor disagree that they ensure the sale of the products in their parlour.

According to the target population 11 of them disagree that these factors affect the acceptance of products and services, and 35 of them agree that these factors affect the acceptance of products and services and 22 neither agree nor disagree that these factors affect the acceptance of products and services. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that these factors affect the acceptance of products and services.

According to the target population 11 of them disagree that these factors affect the acceptance of makeup products, and 39 of them agree that that these factors affect the acceptance of make-up products and 23 neither agree nor disagree that these factors affect the acceptance of make-up products. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that that these factors affect the acceptance of make-up products.

According to the target population 6 of them disagree that these factors affect the acceptance of facial care products, and 46 of them agree that that these factors affect the acceptance of facial care products and 28 neither agree nor disagree that that these factors affect the acceptance of facial care products. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that that these factors affect the acceptance of facial care products.

According to the target population 19 of them disagree that all these factors affect their overall acceptance, and 37 of them agree that all these factors affect their overall acceptance and 25 neither agree nor disagree that c all these factors affect their overall acceptance. Therefore the majority of the population agrees that all these factors affect their overall acceptance

The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test measure of sampling adequacy was used to examine the appropriateness of Factor Analysis. The approximate of Chi-Square is 2213.724 with 276 degrees of freedom, which is significant at 0.05 Level of Significance. The KMO statistic of 0.718 is also large (greater than 0.50).

Hence Factor Analysis is considered as an appropriate technique for further Analysis of the data.

Cronbach alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. Most of the constructs are more than .6 and some are more than 0.7 which shows that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent response to the items of the concerned constructs.

CONCLUSION

In this way cosmetic is a planning amazingly connected to change or improve the excellence of skin, hair, nails, lips and eyes? Each exposable piece of the human life structures is liable to corrective fascination. So cosmetics have been utilized from antiquated circumstances to present day times; it is utilized by females as well as by guys; It turns out to be an integral part of human-beings from support to grave. The Mushroom development of excellence parlours is a declaration for the significance of cosmetics.

Cosmetics have made a few Miss Worlds and Miss Universes. Its application in cine world or film industry is colossal. It has involved a huge place in human life in one way or other. The perpetually expanding populace makes the utilization of cosmetics increase extensively. So promoting of cosmetics ends up plainly aggressive. Ads through broad communications like radio, TV, newspapers and so forth. Advance the offer of cosmetics in a bigger scale. Examine has been completed to enhance its quality and new sorts of cosmetics items are going to the market.

Buyers expect quality cosmetics at sensible cost. So it is the obligation of the Government, makers and go between to supply these necessities of life accessible in a reasonable cost. On the off chance that every one of the proposals and discoveries of this review are tuned in and done, probably the demand example of cosmetics will hold great in India, which lives in towns.

To place it basically the length of human-beings are there in this world, cosmetics would likewise exist and its advertising both in rural and urban regions would have a brilliant future in the days to come.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Entering into the beauty salon industry has a lot of potential in order to increase sales and improve brand awareness of the existing product. In order to introduce new products into the salons we see that giving out free samples to the decision maker and having a workshop in order to introduce the product is very important.

After conducting the survey we have understood that the discounts offered to the salons for the products is also very important. Thus it should be ensured that the discounts offered during a particular season is not less than that offered by the competitors.

Since there is a dependence on certain factors for acceptance of makeup and facial care products the sales strategies should be made taking into these considerations.

Makeup products are more with the quality of the product. The acceptance level also increases with higher rated products. Thus, sales strategies should be formulated based on these criteria's.

Facial care products are more as far as the international brand is concerned. The acceptance level also increases with the well-known international brands. Thus, sales strategies should be formulated based on these criteria's.

The salons do not hesitate to use the products which are costlier but the products used must be of a high quality and well-known brand and we also have known that the products which are purchased are the ones which the customer demands. Here we can know that the customers have a certain products which they want the salon to use.

Customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them, and 31 of them agree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them and

24 neither agree nor disagree that customers hesitate when they use brands that are unknown to them. Therefore it is advisable for their salons to use brands that are known to them.

Also, from the analysis we see that Penetration for Makeup Products is easier and thus the market can be approached with the Makeup Product first.

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